

Increase in Compactness via Resonance for achieving High Strength and Durable Structures

The strength of any structure whether that be roads, bridges, dams , buildings etc depends on compactness of the material during solidification of its elementary composition pastes. Any high strength structure can be achieved if vibration is done in proper frequency in resonance with materials in the paste. If done so in proper manner , all the defects in structural compositions can be avoided and a high strength structure can be achieved. The Resonance Equations are classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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